

THE ROLE OF INNOVATION THINKING IN THE FORMATION OF KNOWLEDGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7329350>

Abstract: the components of any pedagogical system are closely interrelated and are aimed at educational goals. Therefore, the systematic approach in this study was based on the methodological basis, revealing great opportunities in the study of the object, which in turn allows us to explore the object, on this basis, to determine its entire complexity and development, to reveal the peculiarities of education in the system of professional development of pedagogical personnel, its significant opportunities, important links between them. In this article highlights of formation innovative thinking, professional and pedagogical preparation of future professional trainers.

Keywords: knowledge, innovation, pedagogic technology, education.

Аннотация: компоненты любой педагогической системы тесно взаимосвязаны и направлены на достижение образовательных целей. Поэтому системный подход в данном исследовании был основан на методологической основе, раскрывающей большие возможности в изучении объекта, что, в свою очередь, позволяет исследовать объект, на этой основе определять всю его сложность и развитие, выявлять особенности образования в системе профессионального развития педагогических кадров, его значимые возможности, важные связи между ними. В данной статье освещены вопросы формирования инновационного мышления, профессиональной и педагогической подготовки будущих профессиональных тренеров.

Ключевые слова: знания, инновации, педагогические технологии, образование. UDC 37.02 The activity of a person is realized on the basis of a certain inner aspiration, desire, inclination, that is, motivation, whether it is in any character or form, as a result of the realization of this or that goal. This means that the teacher's conscious awareness and aspiration of the social necessity of regular self-activity and improvement of personality is a determining factor in continuous professional development. Therefore, the need for the teacher to have regular knowledge, skills and skills as a mature person, as well as personal confidence in the improvement of the personality and the need for its implementation, an incredibly complex work, thereby becoming the basis for entering into the process of correcting shortcomings in his personality and activities. Activity is such a form of an active attitude of a person to reality, through which a real connection is established with the scientist who lives by

himself. Activity is an activity in which each person is an internal psychic and external physical conscious, purposeful activity. In the organization of activities, the purposeful action of a person is manifested mainly by the interaction of the subject and the object. Activity moves on a need basis. Its content is manifested for the purpose. The goal is an understandable image of the previously achieved result, and human activity is aimed at achieving it. The goal is the level of awareness of the organization and education of the younger generation, which meets the modern requirements of its activity, on the basis of the requirements of reform [1]. Pedagogical activity is a socially – useful acceptable form of human activity, which is purposeful, exquisite, moral and economically harmonious, and begins to prepare young people who are growing up for life in a dream. The purpose of training and retraining of pedagogical personnel in the field of improving the professional skills of the teacher and restructuring it on a scientific basis-is to improve the creative capacity of the teacher, his personal qualities and professional knowledge, skills, and the sole purpose of which is described as the improvement of the quality of education and training of students. The system of professional development of pedagogical personnel is the formation of pedagogical skills on the basis of constantly replenishment, renewal and application of ideological-political, universal, professional, economic, environmental, legal knowledge. Formation of independent and innovative thinking in the preparation of future professional education teachers, the issue of cardinal improvement of the quality of professional and pedagogical training is directly related to its content. Pedagogical knowledge and innovative pedagogical activities are a key component of the future professional vocational training teacher, and in turn, a teacher of vocational education helps to pedagogically orientate the spiritual life of society and material production. Formation of innovative ideas of a future professional trainer is aimed at developing humanitarian, socio-economic, natural-scientific and mathematical knowledge, pedagogical-psychological and general professional and special preparation, the pedagogical activity of a teacher of professional education, its tasks and educational and educational issues, to get a complete understanding of how to interact [2]. Theoretical and methodological and experimental-practical study of the phenomenon of the phenomenon allows to visualize the scientific approach that has arisen in the systematic determination of the level of formation of the innovative thinking of the future teacher of the future profession. In the traditional approach to training, the model of "readiness" knowledge acquired a key role. Knowledge is transmitted from human to

human, as water is poured into a vessel from one vessel. This approach cannot be used in today's rapidly changing society. The ability to read as a fundamental and vital requirement for flexibility to change is that of an educational model that relies on a student to focus on the learning process. In this model, the information is dynamic, with a sense of variability in terms of content. Every time we get acquainted with new concepts and ideas, new knowledge is generated. The information we receive is used to create the structure of our own internal knowledge. The term "knowledge" is a term similar to that used in cognitive psychologists to describe all interconnected imagery of various objects and phenomena present in each one. Knowledge is a "state of understanding" that is specific to a person. This is something we can share in our conversation with another person. We use the information available to us to understand new information. Thus, acquiring knowledge is an active psychological process. Everyone sees a "knowledge-enhancing structure" that connects new ideas to predetermined ideas. That is why information is always connected with the person and unique in some innovative sense. These structures of knowledge or schemes are our personal perceptions about the nature of our world. Together with other systems, we create new knowledge. "Now knowledge is not regarded as manifesting something from outside; this is a separate construction, which makes it possible to compare human knowledge and experience with a cohesive system" [3]. The link between intelligence and thought-building is similar to the link between a car and a driver: a high-powered car can be driven by a poor, and a modest car can be driven easily. Intelligence is the power of intellect, as motor power is a vehicle's ability. According to these conclusions, each of us has a greatly improved reserve capacity. Human beings have not undergone significant changes since the onset of human history, but during this time, through this extraordinary body, humans have been able to create advanced technology that allows them to travel to other planets and extend the life expectancy of more than two times. The only thing that matters is the "brainstorming and processing of the brain"[4]. The ability to read and innovate people has changed the world. According to research results, these modeling techniques are very useful for the development of innovative thinking processes of new learners. Also, personal memoirs are also useful for finding their own space, for example, lack of ability to work with information, or see other flaws. By practicing sound thinking, people learn to work on a specific system - without leaving behind or without the baseless prophecy. The process of verbalization of thinking enables the viewer to evaluate the strategy he chooses and develop

communication skills. The traditional approach to the process of innovative thinking focuses mainly on critical thinking, debate, analysis and logic. These areas are of great importance, but all of them are part of the thinking process.

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